

PECULIARITIES OF BUILDING EFFECTIVE FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT IN THE ENERGY SECTOR

Pecheniuk A.

cand. sc. (econ.), assoc. prof.,

associate professor at the department

of energy-saving technologies and energy management,

Podillia State University, Kamianets-Podilskyi

Abstract

The article reveals the essence of financial management in the context of energy companies; emphasis is placed on the importance of the processes of financial planning and financial analysis in energy; the need to build effective financial control for energy companies is substantiated; the main financial risks in the field of energy were analyzed; the peculiarities of the processes of financing and capital investment in the energy sector were investigated; the main requirements for the formation of an effective strategy for the financial development of energy enterprises are analyzed.

Keywords: financial management, energy, energy companies, financial risks, financial planning, financial analysis, financial control.

The development of the energy sector has a significant impact on the economic condition of the country and the standard of living of its population, since one of the key aspects of well-being in the modern world is the provision of citizens and companies with the necessary energy resources. The energy complex is a capital-intensive industry that requires significant financial investments for the search for raw materials, production and transportation of energy carriers. Therefore, the optimization of production processes and the maximization of profits from invested capital are critically important for the industry, as it is related to the proper level of financial management at enterprises of the energy sector [1].

The essence of financial management in the context of energy companies is the effective management of financial resources and the optimization of their use in order to achieve the company's strategic goals in the energy sector. Key aspects of this entity include:

- financial planning – development of strategic and operational financial plans that take into account the company's needs in investments, development, operating expenses and other financial aspects of activity.
- management of working capital and fixed capital – effective use of capital to ensure the company's current activities and the development of new projects in the energy sector;
- financial analysis – conducting financial analysis to assess the company's financial condition, identify trends and risks, as well as make informed financial decisions;
- risk management – management of financial risks associated with fluctuations in energy prices, changes in legislation, economic factors and other factors that may affect the profitability and financial stability of the company;
- investment strategy – development and implementation of an investment strategy aimed at achieving a competitive advantage and maximizing value for the company's shareholders in the energy market.

Financial management in energy companies is a key component of the successful operation of the enterprise in the conditions of constant changes and challenges inherent in this industry.

The financial stability of energy-generating companies is a key condition for the successful conduct of the country's economic activity, shaping the image of the business entity and serving as its business card. Therefore, one of the most important tasks is to ensure effective management of financial resources, which is closely related to the development and implementation of financial planning. Particular importance is attached to financial planning, as it covers the formation, placement and use of financial resources, as well as obtaining profit on invested capital [1].

Financial planning in the energy sector is the process of developing strategic and operational plans aimed at the effective use of financial resources to achieve the company's goals in this sector. The main aspects of financial planning in energy companies include:

- forecasting of financial flows – assessment of current and future financial flows of the company, taking into account the costs of electricity production, fuel purchase, equipment maintenance, as well as forecasting of income from the sale of energy and other services;
- budgeting – development of budgets for various departments and projects of the company, including capital investments, development of new energy projects, maintenance and other expenses;
- assessment of investment opportunities – analysis of investment projects from the point of view of their profitability and risk, selection of the most promising projects for capital investment;
- working capital and fixed capital management – determining the optimal levels of working and fixed assets, which are necessary to ensure the stable financial condition of the company and meet its current needs;
- risk management – taking into account various financial risks, such as fluctuations in fuel prices, changes in legislation and policy, technical problems

and other factors that may affect the financial stability of the company.

Financial planning in the energy industry is critical to ensure the stable operation of companies in this sector, given the large investments and complexity of energy markets. This process helps companies rationally use financial resources and effectively respond to changes in the internal and external environment.

The main tool for developing the company's financial strategy is financial analysis, which assesses liquidity, solvency and financial stability, determines ways to achieve sustainable development and provides a qualitative approach to the formation of a financial strategy. The implementation of this strategy has a positive effect on the company's activities. The effectiveness and validity of financial analysis create a basis for forecasting various aspects of operational, financial and investment activities, as well as determining promising directions of development. Financial analysis is a complex of scientific and methodical tools that investigate the real financial condition of the enterprise. The use of a wide range of analytical tools allows timely development and implementation of effective anti-crisis measures [2].

Financial analysis in energy companies plays an important role in determining the financial status, efficiency of operations and making informed decisions. Key aspects of financial analysis in this sector include:

- analysis of financial statements - includes the evaluation of financial statements, such as the profit and loss statement, the statement of financial position and the report on the readiness of the company. This analysis allows to assess the general financial condition of the company, its profitability and liquidity;
- comparative analysis – comparison of financial indicators of the energy company with similar indicators of other players on the market or with industry average values. It helps to determine the company's competitive advantages and disadvantages
- analysis of project profitability – evaluation of the effectiveness of investment projects in the field of energy, including projects for the construction of new power plants, the introduction of alternative energy sources and energy conservation. This analysis helps to choose the most profitable and risky projects;
- analysis of liquidity and financial stability – assessment of the company's liquidity and its ability to fulfill financial obligations on time. An analysis of financial stability is also carried out, including an assessment of the level of indebtedness and the degree of financial risk;
- forecasting of financial results – development of forecasts regarding the future financial results of the company based on the analysis of its financial activities and taking into account current and future trends in the energy industry.

Financial analysis in energy companies is an important tool for making informed management decisions, ensuring financial stability and achieving strategic goals in the energy sector. It helps identify problem situations and opportunities to improve the company's performance.

Financial control in the energy industry includes systematic monitoring and analysis of the company's financial results in order to ensure financial stability, effective management of resources and achievement of strategic goals. The main aspects of financial control in energy companies include:

- monitoring of financial indicators – systematic analysis of financial reports and company indicators, such as profit, expenses, turnover of assets, liquidity, etc. It helps identify potential problems and trends in the company's financial activities;
- Internal control – Developed internal control system that includes procedures and control mechanisms to prevent financial abuse, errors and fraud. This may include an audit of internal processes, segregation of duties and a system of internal financial controls.
- analysis of the financial efficiency of projects – assessment of the efficiency of investment projects and the risks associated with them. The cost of the project, potential income and expenses, as well as the internal rate of return (IRR) and the investment payback period are analyzed;
- cost monitoring and budgeting – comparison of actual costs with planned budget indicators to identify deviations and take appropriate corrective measures;
- forecasting and strategic planning – use of analytical methods to forecast future financial results of the company and develop strategies to achieve goals and optimize financial resources.

Financial control in the energy industry helps companies effectively manage their finances, ensures the reliability of financial statements and helps prevent financial risks. It is an important element of risk management and ensuring stability and success in the energy industry.

Modern enterprises of the electric power industry quite often function in unfavorable conditions, which negatively affects their activities due to constant changes in the external environment, a high level of threats and financial risks. One of the most common management mistakes is to evaluate the company's performance only based on current profit and turnover, without taking into account strategic goals and risk forecasting. In the context of the introduction of a new model of the electricity market, the issues of ensuring the financial and economic security of energy supply enterprises through the use of effective risk management mechanisms, methods and tools are becoming particularly relevant [3].

During the period of liberalization of world markets, such processes as globalization, liberalization of the energy market, diversification, decentralization and modernization have a significant impact on the development of the fuel and energy complex of countries.

The essence of the impact of these processes is as follows:

- Globalization contributes to the strengthening of the integration of energy systems at the economic (electricity market, investments), technological (expansion of territories with centralized electricity supply), interstate and intercontinental (interstate and intercontinental energy associations) levels.

- Liberalization of the energy market leads to the growth of deregulation and competition, contributing to the development of regional, interregional and interstate energy markets.

- Diversification leads to an increase in the use of various types of fuel and sources of power supply, as well as various types of power plants.

- Decentralization allows for the implementation of small power plants instead of the construction of large electric power facilities, while maintaining the role of the transport and distribution electric network as an infrastructure that ensures the efficiency, reliability and quality of electricity supply to consumers. This phenomenon is called distributed generation.

- Modernization leads to an increase in the efficiency of traditional technologies and the creation of new highly efficient installations [4].

Threats to the energy security of European countries include physical, economic, social and environmental risks. Physical risks include the possibility of depletion of deposits of major energy resources such as oil and natural gas. In addition, significant natural disasters and geopolitical crises are possible, which can affect the stability of energy supply. Economic risks are associated with the instability of prices for the main energy resources on world markets, which causes imbalances in the financial and trade spheres and creates significant threats to the economic well-being of countries. Social risks are also associated with price fluctuations, which can cause serious dissatisfaction among consumers. The price of gasoline is now as important a factor in stability as the price of bread was two centuries ago. Environmental risks include the possibility of accidents at nuclear and thermal power plants, oil leaks and spills, gas leaks and other accidents at power plants, as well as continuous emissions of pollutants. Special attention is paid to measures to prevent global warming [4].

Among the financial risks faced by energy companies, the following should be highlighted:

- price – changes in the prices of energy carriers, such as oil, natural gas and coal, can significantly affect the profitability of energy companies. For example, a drop in oil prices may reduce revenues from exports or production of electricity using petroleum products;

- political – changes in legislation, tax policies and regulation can have a major impact on energy companies. For example, the introduction of new taxes or emission limits may increase the cost of energy production;

- technical – failures of technical equipment, accidents and other technical problems can lead to a decrease in productivity and an increase in repair and maintenance costs;

- environmental risks – changes in climatic conditions may lead to an increase in the risk of negative impact of natural disasters, such as floods or droughts, on the energy infrastructure;

- market – include changes in energy demand due to economic fluctuations or the impact of alternative energy sources, such as renewable energy sources;

- currency – since many energy companies operate on an international scale, changes in exchange rates can affect their profits and costs.

Preventing and managing these risks is an important element of strategic management for energy companies. This may include diversifying energy sources, using financial instruments to hedge against price fluctuations, and improving technical and operational processes to reduce the risk of technical problems.

Financing and capital investment in the energy sector are key aspects for developing and modernizing infrastructure, supporting innovation and ensuring the stability of energy production. The main methods of financing and capital investment include:

- private capital – attracting private capital by issuing shares or bonds on open markets or through private placements. This may include large investment funds, pension funds, hedge funds and other institutional investors;

- state funding – government subsidies, grants and other forms of funding provided by state or international organizations to support the development of energy infrastructure and initiatives in the field of renewable energy;

- lending – obtaining loans from banks and financial institutions to finance new projects, modernize existing facilities or cover current costs;

- partnership and joint ventures – joint investments with other companies or investors to implement joint projects or develop new technologies;

- internal sources of financing – use of internal resources, such as earnings or generation of internal capital through effective management of working capital and fixed capital.

In recent decades, the issues of global investments in world energy and their impact on the domestic energy market and economy have become increasingly relevant. About two-thirds of all investments go to EU countries, North America and China. At the same time, in developing countries, the lack of strategic policies, insufficient access to financing and fossil fuel subsidies create significant obstacles to investing in energy efficiency. Decisions to invest capital in the energy sector are increasingly being made on the basis of government policy rather than market conditions. In many countries, governments directly influence investments in energy. Practice shows that a significant number of states retain ownership of more than 70% of the world's oil and gas reserves and control almost half of the world's generating capacity through state-owned companies [5].

Capital investments in the energy sector can be aimed at the construction of new power plants, development of renewable energy sources, modernization of existing facilities to increase energy efficiency and reduce emissions, as well as research and implementation of new technologies in the energy sector. It is important to ensure effective management of these capital investments, balancing risks and prospects in order to achieve the company's strategic goals and meet the needs of energy consumers.

To create effective financial management in the energy sector, it is necessary to take into account the current global trends in its development. Constant fluctuations in the prices of energy carriers on the world

market make it difficult to forecast their value for several years ahead. Because of this, many choose systems with optimal adaptability in the use of energy carriers, usually with two energy sources. Even more freedom is provided by the use of one's own household installations for the production of electricity from renewable natural sources.

One of the leading trends in the energy market of the developed countries of the European Union is the decentralization of the production of energy resources, especially electricity, with an emphasis on joint production of heat and electricity. This is due to the rejection of centralized electricity production. For example, in Germany, nuclear power plants are being shut down, and the use of renewable energy plants such as solar, wind and water is increasing. These sources of electricity have uneven production, depending on natural factors: cloud cover, wind speed, seasons, etc. Accordingly, energy consumers can no longer dictate the volume of its production, and generation manages consumption.

However, technologies have emerged that allow even individual private households to become more independent or fully autonomous through electricity generation. This electricity can be accumulated and used at any time and for various needs. The production of electricity is possible in different ways: with the help of individual photocells, fuel cells as part of thermal energy generators or a Stirling engine [6].

The combination of a photovoltaic installation with a heat pump makes the system autonomous and fully dependent on renewable energy sources. The heat generator uses free environmental heat, and the electrical equipment is powered by the current produced by its own photovoltaic installation, using free solar energy.

The generation of electricity using fuel cells in heating equipment is a world novelty. Japan is a leader in the development of such elements, and from there they are supplied en masse to the leading European manufacturers of boiler equipment.

Another cogeneration technology uses the Stirling engine, a heat engine with external heat input. Although this technology is not new, low-power devices designed for domestic use have appeared on the market.

Self-generated electricity can be used for any household needs, for example, to power a washing machine. This function is provided in the equipment menu.

To store electricity, you can use compact wall-mounted lithium batteries, which are already presented in the range of electrical equipment of the world's leading companies. The battery stores excess electricity produced by the generating equipment. If the battery is fully charged and none of the connected consumers are working, electricity is transferred to the public grid.

Today, the market offers compact household batteries capable of storing electricity obtained from the sun. The capacity of such devices, for example, 10 kWh, is sufficient to create energy reserves and its further use. Heat accumulators are also used in systems with electricity accumulators.

Another trend in the heating market, which is gaining momentum, is the improvement of control systems.

Boilers with the most simplified management, thanks to intuitive symbols, appeared on the market.

Some modern heat generators have an energy management module that provides the user with complete information about the amount of energy produced and consumed. This may include data on energy produced by a connected solar installation or gas consumption for heating and hot water [6].

The popularity of managing systems via the Internet is growing, because every year the number of smartphone users and subscribers of global network providers increases. Such remote control systems are becoming more and more accessible and easier to use, even with the complexity of microclimate creation schemes.

Many modern household appliances are equipped for access to the global network. Leading manufacturers offer applications for various portable devices (tablets, smartphones) that can be used to control the microclimate and smart home systems to achieve maximum comfort and energy efficiency.

Modern electronic control technologies allow the use of several types of equipment for energy production, creating so-called hybrid systems. This is especially relevant for heat supply systems.

Hybrid devices are a new category of equipment that allows users not to depend on a single energy source. Thanks to the combination of different energy carriers, the user can always ensure minimum costs at variable energy prices. Two or three energy sources are usually used. In Europe, a combination of liquid, solid or gaseous fuel (traditional boiler) and electricity (heat pump) is popular.

Control systems for such schemes allow you to choose one of two modes of operation of the equipment: economic or ecological. In economic mode, the device automatically selects the optimal operating mode depending on the cost of a specific energy resource (the amount of the tariff is entered by the user) at the moment. For example, it is more profitable to use electricity at a discounted rate at night. In ecological mode, the control system adjusts the operation of the equipment to minimize CO₂ emissions.

Hybrid technologies allow not only to save during the operation of the equipment, but also to optimally select its power. This makes it possible to use wood pellets or gas as the main energy carriers, and cover peak loads with electricity.

Financial development strategies in the energy industry can be aimed at ensuring the stable financial condition of companies, attracting investments for the development of new projects and modernization of existing infrastructure, as well as at stimulating innovation and the introduction of new technologies. Here are some strategies that can be used:

– diversification of energy sources – the development and implementation of various energy sources, such as coal, gas, wind, solar, hydropower, etc., allows companies to reduce dependence on one source and expand their capabilities;

- investments in renewable energy – attraction of investments in renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind energy, which are ecologically clean and sustainable sources of energy;
- energy efficiency – making investments in increasing the energy efficiency of equipment and production processes to reduce energy consumption and costs;
- network development – investing in the development and modernization of energy networks, including the creation of "smart" networks that use advanced technologies to increase efficiency and reliability;
- stimulation of innovation and research: Attracting investments in research and development of new technologies in the field of energy, which contribute to increasing productivity and reducing emissions;
- financial risk management strategies – implementation of strategies to reduce the impact of financial risks, such as fuel price fluctuations, exchange rate changes, political and regulatory risks;
- attraction of alternative financing – use of alternative financing methods, such as cash flows from alternative sources, environmental funds, green investment bonds, etc.

These strategies can be used by companies in the energy industry depending on their specific needs, goals and resources. Implementation of these strategies helps ensure sustainable financial development and competitiveness in the modern energy sector.

Conclusions. Effective financial management requires detailed strategic plans that take into account the company's long-term goals, risks and market opportunities. This ensures flexibility and adaptability in changing market conditions. Systematic analysis and cost control are key to improving the company's performance. The use of modern methods of cost management helps to identify and eliminate unjustified costs, which contributes to increasing profitability. Taking into account all possible financial risks and developing

appropriate measures for their minimization are critically important to ensure the stability and continuity of energy companies. The integration of the latest information technologies and process automation into financial management significantly increases the accuracy and speed of decision-making, and reduces the cost of time and resources. The use of big data analysis tools makes it possible to more accurately forecast financial results, identify trends and make informed and effective management decisions.

References

1. Kostiuk H.V., Usenko O.M. (2013) The main problems of financial planning at energy-generating enterprises and ways to solve them. *Efficient economy*, 4. URL: <http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua/?op=1&z=2000>.
2. Savastieieva O.M. (2021) Financial analysis as a tool for determining the financial strategy of a business entity. URL: <https://dspace.onu.edu.ua/server/api/core/bitstreams/7c21c09c-31e9-47c9-a99d-38f48cea6ced/content>.
3. Levytska A.V., Hrytsenko A.A. (2019) Risk management of the energy company during the transition to a new model of the electricity market. *Economic Journal of Odessa Polytechnic University*, 1(7), 26-31. URL: <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2019/No1/26.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3332881.
4. Karaieva N.V., Voitko S.V., Sorokina L.V. (2013) Risk management of sustainable energy development: information support for decision-making. Kyiv: Alfa Reklama, 308. URL: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/323531417.pdf>.
5. Stepanova A. (2016) Investing in global energy: main trends. *Bulletin of Taras Shevchenko Kyiv National University*, 7(184), 28-32.
6. Kopylov M. (2022). World know-how in energy. AW Therm. URL: <https://aw-therm.com.ua/svi-tovi-nou-hau-v-energetici>.